

D2.1 Communication Toolkit

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<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
RDA	Research Data Alliance
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

The RDA TIGER Communication Toolkit builds on the RDA brand, utilises existing materials and expands them where appropriate. This document outlines communications and marketing materials that will be used during the project lifetime to facilitate RDA TIGER service awareness primarily, but also to support the RDA TIGER individual services.

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1. Introduction

The RDA TIGER project aims to provide services to facilitate and support RDA Working Groups in order to produce quality outputs, resulting in concrete alignment, harmonisation, and standardisation of Open Science developments and technologies globally. In particular, the project will directly contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership, by supporting (via the RDA Working Groups) the international engagement and alignment of policies, technologies, methodologies, practices and other outputs of EOSC-related and other European Open Science developments. It will develop and offer a service platform for these Working Groups, effectively identifying key partners for the groups, and increasing their work efficiency by facilitation, ensuring international connectivity, and other support actions to produce optimum results, and ultimately maximising the impact WG results have on the EOSC, global Open Science, and society.

This document presents the Communication Toolkit developed to support the RDA TIGER services, complementing in particular the Communications Service. Further communication materials can be developed depending on project needs, and in particular based on Quality recommendations and lessons learned after the end of the first year of the project, during which the services are running in their Pilot stage.

RDA TIGER has an integral and comprehensive communications service that works closely with the all RDA TIGER services, providing support for RDA WGs, outward-facing communications activities as well as internal project communications.

It should be noted that the stakeholder analysis (as described in the GA) has been included in D2.2, as it was decided that it complements and informs the communication plan, rather than the communication toolkit.

2. Visual Identity

2.1. Branding - The Research Data Alliance

The RDA TIGER project's visual identity is based on the Research Data Alliance image and brand, incorporating the RDA logo and colour palette. The project's identity is essentially subsumed into that of the Research Data Alliance. It is therefore worth pointing to the RDA Communication Kit, which can be found on the RDA website¹, and may be used for the following:

Colour palette

The RDA colour palette is composed of the following:

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda/communication-kit>

Figure 1. RDA colour palette

Research Data Alliance Communication Kit

The RDA TIGER uses materials either in their current state or updated where appropriate and relevant.

The following existing materials will be used in RDA TIGER promotion activities:

- RDA roll-up banner²
- RDA in a Nutshell (updated monthly by RDA Secretariat)³
- RDA Adoption stories⁴
 - The RDA TIGER project will endeavour to update the RDA Adoption story collection if and when relevant opportunities present themselves through the support of WGs in the finalisation stage.
- RDA TIGER Recommendations and Outputs cards⁵
 - As above, the RDA TIGER project will update the card materials if and when relevant opportunities present themselves through the support of WGs in the finalisation stage.

A number of new materials have also been produced, see section [5. Collaterals](#) in this document.

² https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/RDA_Popup_general_2018_October2018.pdf

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/about-us/communication-kit/adoption-stories>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/Outputs%20Card%20Deck%20-%20September%202022.pdf>

2.2. RDA TIGER logo

The RDA TIGER logo has been co-branded with the EOSC association logo. All file types can be found on the shared RDA TIGER Google Drive⁶.

Table 1. below presents the two versions of the logo with instructions for use.

Table 1. RDA TIGER co-branded logos

	<p>The coloured version of the RDA TIGER logo with the EOSC co-branding should be used in all digital and printed project documentation and collaterals.</p> <p>The logo should be readable, in at least comparable size to other logos. It should not be distorted in any way.</p>
	<p>The monochrome version of the RDA TIGER logo (in black or white) may be used as an alternative stylistic choice when:</p> <p>Co-branding requires it Materials are printed in greyscale</p>

2.3. RDA TIGER illustration

An RDA TIGER illustration has been produced for marketing purposes and it can be found on the shared Google Drive⁷. Table 2 below presents the illustration and notes for use.

Table 2. RDA TIGER ‘mascot’ illustration

	<p>The illustration can be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standalone on unofficial digital and printed materials - Alongside the official EOSC co-branded logo in any official digital or printed materials. <p>Please note that the illustration is a marketing product and not a replacement for the official project logo.</p>
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⁶ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1-RQKkRc_N5JV67InOnb9Wq9yW1AfwwyQ

⁷ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X0zduluMU5m509vYIR6872K-710dgUpY>

3. Online Presence

3.1. Website

As the RDA TIGER works primarily within the RDA community, with its main aim to support the organisation and its Groups, it has been decided that all project pages will be hosted on the Research Data Alliance web platform⁸. The RDA web platform will be used for all official web pages, open call announcements, blogs, news items, etc.

3.2. Social Media

No new social media accounts have been created for the project. Instead, the online presence of the project activities will utilise the existing RDA Europe accounts for Twitter⁹ and LinkedIn¹⁰.

Two hashtags have been created and will be used for project related announcements on social media: #RDATIGER and #ProfessorPounce.

4. Acknowledgments

4.1 Acknowledgment of EU funding

All beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding are required to prominently display the EU emblem and funding statement on all the communication materials and dissemination activities¹¹.

The following EU emblem and funding statement should be displayed:

Figure 2. EU emblem

4.2 Acknowledgment of publications

The following statement should be included in all project-related outputs:

⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger>

⁹ https://twitter.com/RDA_Europe

¹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rda-association/>

¹¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

“This work was developed as part of the RDA TIGER ‘Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions’, funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Grant Agreement 101094406, and we acknowledge the support provided within the project partners and resources”.

As per RDA guidelines, all material associated with the organisation will be made available with CC-BY 4.0 licence.

5. Collaterals

A number of new materials have been developed in order to promote the RDA TIGER services to the RDA Community. These materials have been shared with the project partners and are all available in the RDA TIGER shared Google Drive.

5.1 RDA TIGER poster

In order to promote RDA TIGER service awareness a poster has been created that can be used at physical events and conferences that the project team attends. The poster is available on the RDA TIGER shared Google Drive¹², and it will be periodically updated according to new needs for announcements, open call promotion, etc.

Figure 3. RDA TIGER poster developed for RDA P20.

¹² https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RFkiBzzlRqaxe-9XkvxEoRNeMF-XEX_V/view?usp=sharing

5.2 RDA TIGER business cards

A set of RDA TIGER business cards was created, printed and distributed as a part of the marketing campaign to promote RDA TIGER services to the RDA Community during RDA Plenary 20 in Gothenburg in March 2023. The card design can be seen below in Figure 4.

Figure 4. RDA TIGER business cards.

5.3 RDA TIGER graphics

A set of graphics have been developed as part of the RDA TIGER branding. The graphics are used to promote the RDA TIGER service platform mainly on the RDA website, but also on presentations, social media, posters, flyers, etc. Examples of the graphics can be seen in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Examples of RDA TIGER branded graphics

5.4 RDA TIGER collaterals

For the purpose of enhancing service awareness and promoting the project to the potential service users present at RDA Plenary 20, the following materials were created and distributed:

- RDA TIGER stickers
- RDA TIGER badges
- RDA TIGER lanyards

Figure 6. RDA TIGER badges

6. PowerPoint template

A branded slide deck on PowerPoint has been created and will be used for all project-related presentations. The template is available for all project partners on the RDA TIGER shared Google Drive¹³.

Figure 7. RDA TIGER branded slide deck

¹³ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1zcLi3tVX-SN_Y3c66McpXOGWjb_XQqKa/edit?usp=sharing&oid=108777747194795176299&rtpof=true&sd=true

7. Zenodo Community

An RDA TIGER Zenodo Community¹⁴ has been created, which will host all RDA TIGER deliverables and outputs.

8. Conclusion

The RDA TIGER project has been developed with its primary aim being to support and facilitate the work of the RDA and its community. Therefore, it has been decided that the project's identity and branding will adopt (and occasionally expand on) that of the RDA Foundation. This Communication Toolkit has described RDA materials already in place that the project will leverage, and outlined new collaterals created for the purpose of promoting RDA TIGER Service awareness. As with any project, more materials will be developed as needed and following the conclusion of the RDA TIGER Pilot stage and any Quality recommendations and lessons learned resulting from this. This document will be updated accordingly as and when needed.

¹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/rda-tiger>

